

Assign Weights to Ranking Factors under Group Popularity for Library and Information System based on the CRITIC Strategy

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Abstract

The collection of libraries printed and electronic materials are increasing day by day. OPAC or Web OPAC considers a few ranking factors and factors that are not too pinpointed. That is why users are not satisfied and the presentation of search results is not sophisticated as far as relevancy is concerned. So, there is a need for new thinking in the Information Retrieval (IR) system which considers almost all ranking factors and will produce search results according to best matches in descending order. The purpose of this research paper is to discuss the ranking factors under group Popularity and assign weight to each individual ranking factor based on users' assessment using the CRiteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation (CRITIC) strategy. A thorough study of the literature review helps us understand that six groups of ranking factors are adapted from search engines and may be used in Library and Information System (LIS) search results ranking. Here, we have considered the ranking factors under the popularity group and made a framework to incorporate the factors after assigning weights. This is the first approach in the field of information retrieval to consider ranking factors concerned with modern practice and assign weights to the factors using the neutrosophic CRITIC strategy. It is also helpful when designing a ranking model for a library information system, designing discovery tools, or discussing with an ILS vendor.

Keywords: CRITIC, Information Retrieval, Library and Information System, Next-Generation Catalogue, Ranking Factors

Introduction

Information Retrieval (IR) is typically a two-step process, firstly potentially relevant documents are identified, and then identified documents are ranked. Users try to find out libraries' local and remote collections through the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) or Web version which is known as Web-OPAC. This kind of search system has some shortcomings as it is not sufficiently user-centered and the presentation of the results lacks sophistication [1]. Nowadays, library catalogues or discovery systems have implemented search engine technology to meet users' expectations in terms of searching and finding information [2]-[5]. Ranking involves combining a set of heuristics derived from the corpus, the result set, and individual documents. There are so many ranking Factors (RFs) identified by many researchers and all are categorized or grouped into six (6), like text statistics, popularity, freshness, locality & availability, content properties, and background [6]. Library Information Systems (LISs) now use only a few ranking factors to provide search results according to relevancy but not based on the users' preference. As ultimately ranking the search results for the user of the Information system, we have

considered users' preferences as well as that of IR subject experts. The Library and Information Management System software has been using some common fields or factors for the relevant order of the search results. We have considered a few ranking factors and assigned weights and ranked them in descending order using CRITERIA Importance Through Inter-criteria Correlation (CRITIC) strategy which is very popular and suitable for this perspective. The CRITIC strategy is based on the standard deviation [7] which uses correlation analysis to measure the value of each criterion. CRITIC strategy is very much well-known in Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM).

Uncertainty involves in every sphere of real-life problems. Ranking factors inherently involve uncertainty, indeterminacy, and inconsistency. To deal with uncertainty Zadeh [8] developed the Fuzzy Set (FS). Smarandache [9] extended the FS to the Neutrosophic Set (NS) which is actually a generalization of different types of FSs and Intuitionistic FSs (IFSs) [10]. The term "neutrosophy" means "knowledge of neutral thought" [9]. NS [9] is characterized by a truth-membership degree, an indeterminacy-membership degree, and a falsity-membership degree independently. Wang, Smarandache, Zhang, and Sunderraman [11] grounded a subclass of NS called Single-Valued NS (SVNS) which is more popular in MCDM problems. The use of CRITIC strategy in the SVNS environment for IR systems as well as LISs is not found in the literature.

The paper describes a few ranking factors under the group popularity and out of them five popularity ranking factors have been considered for the study. Using CRITIC strategy in the SVNS environment, we assign weights to the Ranking Factors (RFs) and finally arrange the RFs in descending order according to their weight.

In section II, we discuss the related literature. In section III, we present the objectives of the study. In section IV, we present the methodology used for the study. In section V, we develop the CRITIC strategy under group decision-makers using Single Valued Neutrosophic Number Weighted Geometric Aggregation (SVNNWGA) operator. In section VI, we show the calculation and obtained results. Section VII concludes the paper.

Literature review

In this section, we have done a literature search on Library materials ranking factors, popularity group ranking factors, the process of assigning weights to the criteria, and the CRITIC strategy. Freshness was the most-used ranking criterion [12] in catalogues. For a real ranking [13], OPACs usually employ only standard text matching. There are some ideas to improve the relevance ranking that go beyond pure text matching. Flimm [14] proposed popularity ranking factors in catalogues for relevance ranking. According to Mercun & Zumer [15] and Sadeh [16] "circulation statistics, book review data, the number of downloads, and the number of print copies owned by the institutions" are also to be considered for ranking search results in the LIS.

In many cases, users are not willing or they are not able to look through the whole result sets. So quality ranking reduces to a crucial factor [12]. Behnert and Lewandowski [6] categorized all ranking factors into six (6) groups namely, text statistics, popularity, freshness, locality & availability, content properties, and user background. Catalogues rank usually search results based on date of publication but the additional inclusion of popularity-based factors was highly promising to yield valuable benefits [17]. Various criterion weighting procedures have been established in the literature [18] for the MADM process. The methodologies for calculating weights are divided into two categories: objective weight and subjective weight [19]. According to Diakoulaki, Mavrotas & Papayannakis [7] the CRITIC approach is one of the weighting models that uses the standard deviation and correlation coefficient to measure the value of each attribute and generate the weights of attributes for the MADM, MAGDM techniques. A new method was found in the paper [20] where SVNN-CRITIC and SVNN-ARAS methods were developed for the MCDM problems by integrating SVNNs into CRITIC and ARAS methods.

A few works were found on the CRITIC method in SVNS environment to solve MCDM problems of different fields but no such work was found to assign weight to the RFs considered for relevance ranking of search results in LIS.

Objectives

The main objective of the present study is as follows.

To develop the novel CRITIC strategy using (SVNNWGA) in the SVNS environment and evaluate the weights of the ranking factors of the group popularity in LISs.

Methodology

The study has been done on the thorough review of the relevant documents to obtain popularity ranking factors so far identified and applicable for LISs by researchers. A questionnaire has been prepared and sent to experts for their opinion based on the

five-point Likert scale. The data collected on the linguistic terms were transformed into Single Valued Neutrosophic Numbers (SVNNs) for calculations.

CRITIC Strategy using SVNNWGA Operator for neutrosophic environment

Let $M = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_r\}$ be a collection of r alternatives and $\hat{A} = \{\hat{A}_1, \hat{A}_2, \dots, \hat{A}_s\}$ be a collection of s attributes. Let $\beta = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p)$ be the weight vector of the P Decision Makers (DMs) involved in the problem

with $\beta_p \in [0, 1], \sum_{p=1}^P \beta_p = 1$. The weight calculating CRITIC strategy for SVNNs is developed using the following

steps (see Figure 1):

Step 1: Construct the decision matrices

Suppose that $H^p = (h_{lm}^p)_{r \times s}$ is the p-th decision matrix where information about the alternative M_l is provided by the p-th decision maker with respect to the attribute \hat{A}_m .

The p-th decision matrix is defined as follows:

$$H^p = (h_{lm}^p)_{r \times s} = \begin{pmatrix} h_{11}^p & h_{12}^p \dots & h_{1s}^p \\ h_{21}^p & h_{22}^p \dots & h_{2s}^p \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ h_{r1}^p & h_{r2}^p \dots & h_{rs}^p \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $l = 1, 2, \dots, r, m = 1, 2, \dots, s, p = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

Step 2: Standardize the decision matrices

To remove the effects originated from different physical dimensions, the decision matrices $(h_{lm}^p)_{r \times s}$ are standardized as follows:

i. For benefit criterion

$$h_{lm}^p = h_{lm}^p = \langle t_{lm}^p, i_{lm}^p, f_{lm}^p \rangle (p = 1, 2, \dots, P), \text{ no change occurs.}$$

ii. For cost criterion, complement is taken as follows:

$$h_{lm}^p = \langle f_{lm}^p, 1 - i_{lm}^p, t_{lm}^p \rangle (p = 1, 2, \dots, P) \quad (2)$$

Step 3: Aggregate the decision matrices using the SVNNWGA operator

$$\begin{aligned} &SVNNWGA_{\beta} (h_{lm}^1, h_{lm}^2, \dots, h_{lm}^p) \\ &= \beta_1 h_{lm}^1 \otimes \beta_2 h_{lm}^2 \otimes \dots \otimes \beta_p h_{lm}^p \\ [21] &= \prod_{p=1}^P \beta_p h_{lm}^p \\ &= \left\langle \prod_{p=1}^P (t_{lm}^p)^{\beta_p}, 1 - \prod_{p=1}^P (1 - i_{lm}^p)^{\beta_p}, 1 - \prod_{p=1}^P (1 - f_{lm}^p)^{\beta_p} \right\rangle \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

The aggregated decision matrix Δ can be presented as:

$$\Delta = (\rho_{lm})_{r \times s} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{11} & \rho_{12} & \dots & \rho_{1s} \\ \rho_{21} & \rho_{22} & \dots & \rho_{2s} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{r1} & \rho_{r2} & \dots & \rho_{rs} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where ρ_{lm} is the aggregated element of neutrosophic decision matrix Δ for $l = 1, 2, \dots, r, m = 1, 2, \dots, s$.

Step 4: Determine the score value of each SVNN

The score value of each SVNN of (4) is obtained using the formula [21]

$$\rho'_{lm} = \text{Sc}(\rho_{lm}) = \frac{2 + t_{lm} - i_{lm} - f_{lm}}{3} \quad (5)$$

$l=1, 2, \dots, r; m=1, 2, \dots, s.$

Step 5: Calculate the standard deviations

The standard deviation of each attribute is calculated as:

$$\sigma_m = \sqrt{\frac{1}{r-1} \sum_{l=1}^r (\rho'_{lm} - \bar{\rho}'_m)^2} \quad (6)$$

$m = 1, 2, \dots, s$

$$\bar{\rho}'_m = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{l=1}^r \rho'_{lm} \quad (7)$$

$l=1, 2, \dots, r; m=1, 2, \dots, s.$

Step 6: Calculate correlation coefficients

The Calculate correlation coefficient ϕ_{mn} between the attributes is obtained as

$$\text{follows } \phi_{mn} = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^r (\rho'_{lm} - \bar{\rho}'_m)(\rho'_{ln} - \bar{\rho}'_n)}{\sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^r (\rho'_{lm} - \bar{\rho}'_m)^2 (\rho'_{ln} - \bar{\rho}'_n)^2}} \quad (8)$$

$m = 1, 2, \dots, s; n = 1, 2, \dots, s.$

$$\bar{\rho}'_n = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{l=1}^r \rho'_{ln} \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{\rho}'_m = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{l=1}^r \rho'_{lm}$$

Step 7: Calculate the index (C_m)

The index (C_m) is determined as:

$$C_m = \sigma_m \sum_{n=1}^s (1 - \phi_{mn}) \quad (10)$$

Step 8: Calculate the weights of the attributes

The weights of the attributes are determined using the following formula:

$$\omega_m = \frac{C_m}{\sum_{m=1}^s C_m} \quad (11) \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, s.$$

Step 9: Ranking the attributes based on their weights

The attributes are ranked in descending order based on their weights.

Figure 1: CRITIC Strategy for SVNNs

Data , Calculations and results

The display of search results according to the relevance order is very much difficult as the relevance is a subjective matter and differs from one individual to the next. Here we have considered five RFs like Circulation Rate (\hat{A}_1), Number of Copies (\hat{A}_2), Reputation of Publisher (\hat{A}_3), Author's Social Profile (\hat{A}_4) and Seniority of Author in Publication and Research (\hat{A}_5). We have considered four documents as alternatives (M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4) of a library and data related to the documents. Here all five criteria are benefit type criteria. We have considered three users: ($\hat{S}_1, \hat{S}_2, \hat{S}_3$) those who are doing research work in their own field of study, and the weight vector of the three DMs is considered as $w=(0.35, 0.35, 0.3)$ respectively. The linguistic terms are converted into SVNNs [22] (see Table 1).

Table 1: Linguistic terms for the rating of attributes

Linguistic Terms	SVNNs
Very Important (5)	$\{0.90, 0.10, 0.10\}$
Important (4)	$\{0.80, 0.20, 0.15\}$
Medium (3)	$\{0.50, 0.40, 0.45\}$
Unimportant (2)	$\{0.35, 0.60, 0.70\}$
Very unimportant (1)	$\{0.10, 0.80, 0.90\}$

We construct the following decision matrices (see Table 2) and proceed to do the calculations according to the steps outlined in Section V.

Table 2: Decision Matrix

D M	Alternatives	\hat{A}_1	\hat{A}_2	\hat{A}_3	\hat{A}_4	\hat{A}_5
J_1	M_1	$\langle 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$
	M_2	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$
J_1	M_3	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$
	M_4	$\langle 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$
J_1	M_5	$\langle 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$
	M_6	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$
J_2	M_7	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$
	M_8	$\langle 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.80, 0.20, 0.15 \rangle$
J_2	M_9	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.10, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle$	$\langle 0.10, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$
	M_{10}	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.10, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.10, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle$
J_2	M_{11}	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$
	M_{12}	$\langle 0.35, 0.60, 0.70 \rangle$	$\langle 0.10, 0.80, 0.90 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.50, 0.40, 0.45 \rangle$

Table 3: Aggregated Decision Matrix

	\hat{A}_1	\hat{A}_2	\hat{A}_3	\hat{A}_4	\hat{A}_5
M_1	$\langle 0.6779, 0.2944, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5296, 0.4124, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3637, 0.5228, 0.6 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3637, 0.5228, 0.6 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3965, 0.5390, 0.6 \rangle$
M_2	$\langle 0.5296, 0.4124, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2723, 0.6256, 0.7 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5000, 0.4000, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4871, 0.4687, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3085, 0.5685, 0.6 \rangle$
M_3	$\langle 0.6948, 0.2661, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4493, 0.4687, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5296, 0.4124, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4413, 0.4794, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5296, 0.4124, 0.4 \rangle$
M_4	$\langle 0.6779, 0.2944, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3637, 0.5228, 0.6 \rangle$	$\langle 0.6948, 0.2661, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5000, 0.4000, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5894, 0.3364, 0.3 \rangle$

Table 4: Score Value of the Aggregated Decision Matrix

	\hat{A}_1	\hat{A}_2	\hat{A}_3	\hat{A}_4	\hat{A}_5
M_1	0.6770	0.5504	0.4083	0.4083	0.4095
M_2	0.5504	0.3045	0.5500	0.4864	0.3566
M_3	0.7249	0.4797	0.5504	0.4689	0.5504
M_4	0.6770	0.4083	0.7249	0.5500	0.6312

Table 5: Value of Standard Deviation

	\hat{A}_1	\hat{A}_2	\hat{A}_3	\hat{A}_4	\hat{A}_5
σ_{mn}	0.0748	0.1050	0.1296	0.0583	0.1263

Table 6: Correlation Coefficient

	\hat{A}_1	\hat{A}_2	\hat{A}_3	\hat{A}_4	\hat{A}_5
\hat{A}_1	1.0000	0.7950	0.0234	-0.1122	0.6899
\hat{A}_2	0.7950	1.0000	-0.5153	-0.6248	0.1775
\hat{A}_3	0.0234	-0.5153	1.0000	0.9906	0.7381
\hat{A}_4	-0.1122	-0.6248	0.9906	1.0000	0.6391
\hat{A}_5	0.6899	0.1775	0.7381	0.6391	1.0000

Table 7: Index C Matrix

	\hat{A}_1	\hat{A}_2	\hat{A}_3	\hat{A}_4	\hat{A}_5
\hat{A}_1	0.0000	0.2050	0.9766	1.1122	0.3101
\hat{A}_2	0.2050	0.0000	1.5153	1.6248	0.8225
\hat{A}_3	0.9766	1.5153	0.0000	0.0094	0.2619
\hat{A}_4	1.1122	1.6248	0.0094	0.0000	0.3609
\hat{A}_5	0.3101	0.8225	0.2619	0.3609	0.0000

Step 1: We construct the decision matrices given in Table II.

Step 2: Using Eq. (2), we calculate the standardized decision matrices. But here all the attributes are benefit type, so the decision matrix and standardized matrix are the same.

Step 3: Using Eq. (3), we now aggregate the standardized decision matrices. Table III provides the aggregated decision matrix.

Step 4: Using the formula (5), the score value of each SVNN is calculated and presented in Table IV.

Step 5: Eq. (6) is used to determine the standard deviation, and the results are given in Table V.

Step 6: The correlation coefficients between attributes are determined by utilizing Eq. (8) and shown in Table VI.

Step 7: We evaluate the indices C_m using Eq. (10) and present them in Table VII

Step 8: The weights of the attributes are determined by utilizing Eq. (11) and are presented as:

$\omega_1 = 0.1398$, $\omega_2 = 0.3141$, $\omega_3 = 0.2570$, $\omega_4 = 0.1300$ and $\omega_5 = 0.1591$.

Step 9: The attributes are ranked in descending order depending on their weights.

$\omega_2 > \omega_3 > \omega_5 > \omega_1 > \omega_4$

Conclusion

This paper discusses the ranking factors under group Popularity and assign weight to each individual ranking factor based on users' assessment using the CRITIC strategy. Here, we have considered the ranking factors under the popularity group and made a framework to incorporate all the factors after assigning weights. This is the first approach in the field of information retrieval to consider SVNN environment with modern practice and assign weights to the factors using the CRITIC strategy. It is also helpful when designing a ranking model for a library information system, designing Discovery Tools, or discussing with an ILS vendor.

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